

The Audience's Use of TV Channel Pages on Social Media Platforms to Increase Political Awareness

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Abstract: Research title: The audience's use of TV channel pages on social media platforms to increase political awareness. This study aims to investigate how the audience uses TV channel pages on social media platforms to increase political awareness. After the media integration between satellite channels and social media sites, these platforms have become an effective tool for disseminating information and interacting with the audience.

As well as knowing the use of satellite channel pages on social media sites increases the political awareness of the audience, as well as how to analyze the impact of these pages on increasing political awareness among the audience, as well as knowing the types of political content that most influence the audience. The survey method was used, which is considered the appropriate method for studying through the questionnaire tool with a sample of followers of TV channel pages on social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter and Instagram, where the results showed that the target audience uses TV channel pages on social media sites to obtain reliable and fast political information. These pages also contribute to increasing political awareness by providing diverse and comprehensive content. Also, interaction with political content on these pages enhances the audience's understanding of political issues.

Keywords: The audiences, TV channel pages, social media platforms, political awareness.

Introduction:

Media, in its various forms and techniques, plays a significant role in shaping individuals' personalities and altering their thoughts and attitudes toward various societal issues.

Media can have either a positive role in character building or a negative one. With technological and scientific advancements, the field of media has undergone significant development in its techniques, methods, and tools, contributing to changes in many ideas and orientations among members of society.

Satellite channels have emerged as one of the most important modern media technologies, becoming widespread globally across various levels. Their numbers have reached tens of thousands, broadcasting diverse programs around the clock without interruption, and exerting a considerable influence on various aspects of social and political life worldwide.

Subsequently, social media platforms emerged, marking a significant development unrestricted by geographical boundaries and accessible to all segments of society. These platforms provided communication features that other media lacked.

Society, as a collective and diverse entity, is shaped through shared efforts, even amidst differences. This entity is both possible and essential due to the interconnectedness fostered by social media, which has arisen from technological advancements.

The importance of social media lies in its ability to enable continuous communication, share ideas, opinions, and experiences, follow current events, engage with stories, interact with posts, and raise public political awareness.

Consequently, audiences have increasingly relied on these platforms to stay informed about daily political events, which highlights the need to examine how the content shared by satellite channels on social media impacts the public's political awareness.

Chapter One: Methodological Framework

First: Research Problem

Social media networks have played a crucial role in raising public awareness of political issues. The pages of satellite channels on these platforms have become significant platforms for disseminating diverse media content, showcasing evident and multifaceted interactivity.

The research problem is defined as: (An ambiguous situation, idea, or concept that requires investigation or scientific study to understand its premises, establish relationships between its components, evaluate its current outcomes, and reshape it based on study findings, placing it within a scientific framework) (Al-Hameed, 2000).

The researchers identified the central research question as follows:

How do the social media pages of television channels contribute to increasing political awareness?

From this central question, several sub-questions arise:

1. Does the audience's use of satellite channel pages on social media enhance their political awareness?
2. Does the researched audience rely on satellite channel pages on social media to follow political events?
3. What are the preferred channels that the audience follows to increase their political awareness?
4. What are the main types of interaction with the content posted on satellite channel pages on social media?

Second: Importance of the Study

The significance of this study stems from its focus on the subject (the use of television channel pages on social media platforms to enhance political awareness). The importance lies in the researchers' interest in this topic, which is considered vital for providing university libraries with modern sources linking the integration of social media and satellite channels, aiming to align with technological advancements.

This study is crucial as it connects the variable of social media to satellite channels. It offers significant data on social media to stakeholders in Iraqi satellite channels, enabling them to modify and improve their content, particularly in political news.

The study also seeks to understand consumption patterns of political news through satellite channel pages and measure audience interactions with these topics.

Third: Research Objectives

1. To determine whether the use of satellite channel pages on social media enhances the audience's political awareness.
2. To investigate the extent to which the researched audience relies on satellite channel pages on social media to follow political events.
3. To identify the preferred channels that the audience follows to increase their political awareness.
4. To examine the main types of interaction with the content posted on satellite channel pages on social media.

Fourth: Study Type and Methodology

This study is classified as a descriptive study, aiming to describe events, individuals, beliefs, attitudes, values, goals, and behavioral patterns exhibited by the audience in consuming and interacting with political news. The study provides a clear picture of the phenomenon under investigation, gathering data to enhance understanding and predict its occurrence (Al-Najjar, 2009).

The researchers employed the survey method, a scientific approach to gathering information. The survey methodology is widely used in media studies, particularly descriptive research.

Fifth: Research Population and Sample

The research population consists of the Iraqi audience that follows the pages of Iraqi satellite channels, which frequently post political topics. The research population is defined as (the entire group of elements the researcher aims to generalize the findings to concerning the studied problem) (Makawi, 1987).

Since the entire population is vast and difficult to reach, the study focuses on the accessible population. A purposive sample was selected, targeting audiences who closely follow the pages of news satellite channels on social media. The researchers distributed a questionnaire to 110 individuals from the audience in Dhi Qar Governorate who actively follow these pages.

Translation to Academic English:

Sixth: Research Boundaries and Scope

- **Temporal Boundaries:** The research period extends from July 1, 2024, to October 1, 2024, during which the questionnaire was completed.
- **Spatial Boundaries:** The research focuses on Dhi Qar Governorate, Iraq.
- **Topical Boundaries:** The study addresses the audience's use of satellite channel pages on social media platforms.

Seventh: Definition of Terms

1. **Social Media:** Websites on the internet that use specific applications designed for communication with other users or connecting with individuals who share common interests (Dewing, 2010).
2. **Television Channels:** Channels transmitted via a network of satellites orbiting the Earth in predefined known paths, typically identified by angle and direction on a compass, which determine the orientation for broadcasting groups of satellite channels (Al-Nabi, 2010).
3. **Political Awareness:** A set of values, attitudes, and political principles that enable individuals to participate effectively in the situations and problems of their society, analyze and judge them, determine their positions, and motivate them to act toward developing and changing them (Al-Jamal, 1996).

Eighth: Previous Studies

The researchers categorized previous studies according to their relevance to the research variables, emphasizing their importance. Three studies were selected as they meet the study requirements, as follows:

1. Fahmy's Study (2019):

- **Title:** Audience Interactivity with Egyptian Satellite Channel Pages on Facebook: A Study of the Reflections of Interactivity on the Construction of the Media Agenda.
- **Type:** Unpublished Master's Thesis, Cairo University, Faculty of Media, 2019.
- **Objective:** The study aimed to identify the characteristics of comments raised regarding issues presented on the official pages of satellite channels (e.g., the "Bawraqah wa Qalam" program page on Ten TV, a private satellite channel, and the "Hamzat Wasl" program page on Egypt News Channel).

➤ **Findings:** The study revealed that likes ranked first among interactive forms used by audiences on the Facebook pages of the two programs in the sample, at 65.5%. Comments intended to express opinions ranked first on both pages at 59.6%, followed by sarcastic comments at 32.9%. The interactivity of official program pages reflected the media agenda, influenced by the editorial policies of the channels and program goals. In some cases, comments from these official pages were considered by program teams.

2. Abdul-Latif's Study (2018):

➤ **Title:** Factors Influencing Interactivity on Egyptian Television Program Pages via Social Media Platforms.

➤ **Focus:** This study examined the factors affecting interactivity on program pages on social media platforms, which have become increasingly widespread.

➤ **Methodology:** The study employed both field and analytical survey methods, targeting a purposive sample of 400 young people.

➤ **Key Findings:** The audience interacted highly with political programs (54%), followed by entertainment programs (42%). Among respondents, 40% believed the performance of program hosts in talk shows was "very good," 33% rated it as "good," 16% as "excellent," and 4.3% as "weak."

3. Al-Tamimi's Study (2015):

➤ **Title:** Youth Use of Social Media and Its Relationship with Television Exposure: A Survey Study on High School Students in Wasit Governorate.

➤ **Objective:** The study explored youth use of social media and its relationship with television exposure, addressing the challenges faced by television in light of the growing popularity of social media and the increasing number of users, especially among youth—the group most active on social media platforms according to many studies.

➤ **Findings:**

➤ High social media usage among youth: 94.7% of respondents used social media platforms, while only 5.3% did not.

➤ Facebook was the most widely used platform, followed by YouTube and then Twitter.

➤ High television viewership among youth: 97.5% of respondents watched television channels.

➤ The study also highlighted the competitive and complementary relationship between social media platforms and television, examining how social media use impacts television exposure and identifying youth interest in the content produced by television on social media.

Translation to Academic English:

Abdul-Fattah's Study (2013):

➤ **Title:** Interactivity in Online Journalistic and Social Media Platforms and Its Relationship with Social and Political Interaction Among Egyptian Youth Within the Framework of Media Richness and Social Presence Theories: A Comparative Applied Study.

➤ **Objective:** The study aimed to observe and describe interactivity through its tools, indicators, and features on social media platforms. It examined functional interactivity on these platforms and the perceived interactivity among the youth sample, analyzing the extent of their use of such platforms and its impact on their social and political interaction.

➤ **Findings:**

The study highlighted the superiority of social networking platforms over online journalistic platforms in providing information. Social media ranked as the top platforms accessed by youth, with 86.8% of respondents browsing these platforms. Facebook was the most used platform, with 92.5% of the

sample using it, followed by YouTube (81.5%). Additionally, 51.8% of the respondents indicated that their use of online journalistic and social media platforms somewhat influenced their interaction with family, friends, neighbors, and colleagues.

Chapter Two

Social Media and Its Relationship with Increasing Political Awareness

First: Social Media

In recent decades, platforms known as “social media” have emerged on the internet. These platforms are a natural outcome of rapid and immense advancements in technology and media. They fulfill the need for individuals to establish human relationships and facilitate broader interactive dialogue, reconnecting individuals, such as school or university classmates.

These platforms were established to encourage dialogue and free expression of thoughts consistent with one’s beliefs, to share ideas with others, to promote specific opinions, or to showcase common interests (Al-Faisal, 2014).

Some define social media as online communities that rely on specific applications for each platform. These platforms host various content formats that can be presented in diverse forms (Hisnlin, 2016). According to the Webster-Merriam Dictionary, social media is defined as: Electronic forms of communication, such as social networking websites and microblogs, enabling users to create electronic connections for sharing information, data, ideas, and other media (Kanwar, 2012).

Social media platforms are also described as services that build and strengthen social networks, facilitating communication between people with shared interests and activities.

Second: Features of Social Media

1. **Interactivity and Participation:** Social media platforms are characterized by interactivity, allowing users to exchange opinions, ideas, and information, comment on news published on these platforms, and share personal interests and hobbies such as art and sports.
2. **Revolutionary Media Transition:** Social media has revolutionized traditional media, expanding its horizons and offering users greater opportunities to influence and cross borders with minimal restrictions or oversight.
3. **Diversity:** Social media emphasizes diversity in formats, technologies, and characteristics that were previously limited to traditional media.
4. **Openness:** Social media platforms allow audience comments and participation without imposing restrictions on interactions or content browsing, making them accessible and open to the public (Youssef, 2013).
5. **Fostering Connections:** Social media enables individuals to form and maintain friendships, exchange interests, and engage with content, contributing to the creation of virtual communities. These platforms have enhanced global connectivity and developed a worldwide communication network (Ibrahim, 2012).

Third: Importance of Social Media

Social media platforms are among the modern, advanced tools that promote values of knowledge, critique, introspection, and dialogue—values fundamental to any cultural development project.

Given their significance in various spheres of life—media, social, political, and cultural—social media platforms play a vital role as sources of information and news. These platforms emphasize user-driven content, allowing individuals to express their identity and interact with others’ ideas.

The importance of social media lies in its ability to permeate individuals’ and groups’ lives swiftly and seamlessly, offering unconventional means of accessing information and knowledge. It fosters interaction and integration within the framework of camaraderie and friendship (Haroun, 2017).

Social media has also become a critical means of communication, turning individuals into media institutions capable of publishing content anytime and in any manner they choose. Social media introduced the concept of "citizen journalism," enabling individuals to document events, write about them, or share images on social platforms. News outlets and television channels, eager for updates from inaccessible regions, quickly utilize this content.

Translation to Academic English:

Fourth: Social Media and Political Awareness

The concept of social media is a subject of debate due to the varying opinions and perspectives surrounding it. This reflects the technological advancements associated with its use, encompassing all tools utilized by groups or individuals on social media platforms (Atif, 2014).

This form of media operates in the virtual space and utilizes social media platforms as tools, managed by institutions and individuals with varying capacities and resources. It is characterized by its rapid dissemination, low cost, and significant influence (Kanaan, 2015).

These large-scale operations on social media are defined by their diverse network configurations, which enable content availability through multiple links and tools. These tools assist users in accessing content, granting them the freedom to use, select, and interact with various elements, aligning with their needs, interests, and preferences, and achieving the goals of publication and distribution on these platforms (Al-Hameed, 2007).

The influence of satellite channels on public opinion is self-evident. Regardless of whether an individual is educated or illiterate, they are exposed to, observe, and participate in news through social media platforms, leveraging them to enhance their political awareness (Fayyad, 2003).

The relationship between satellite channels and political awareness is embodied through reliance on media as a source of political awareness, shaping public opinion. On the other hand, media outlets receive both official and unofficial information from political systems to disseminate it. However, the cooperative and mutually dependent relationship between political systems and media can evolve into tension. Political systems may seek to impose control, while media plays the role of a guardian for citizens' interests by exposing errors and illegal practices. Nonetheless, neither entity can achieve its objectives without reliance on the other (Saud, 2010).

Chapter Three

The Practical Aspect

Study Hypotheses:

1. There is a correlation between the audience's use of television channel pages on social media platforms and an increase in their political awareness.
2. The use of television channel pages on social media platforms to follow political content may contribute to enhancing individuals' level of political awareness.
3. The type of political content provided by television channel pages on social media platforms (e.g., news, political analyses, discussions, programs, and interactions) is positively associated with increasing political awareness among the Iraqi audience.
4. There is a positive correlation between engagement (e.g., comments, shares, and likes) with political content on television channel pages on social media platforms and evidence of increased political awareness among the surveyed sample.

Translation to Academic English:

Table 1: Gender Frequency Distribution

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	69	69%
Female	31	31%
Total	100	100%

From Table 1, it is observed that the percentage of males is 69%, while females make up 31%. This indicates a relatively balanced ratio between males and females, which may reflect a shared interest in television channel pages on social media as a means of increasing political awareness.

Table 2: Age Group Distribution

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage
18–28	66	66%
19–29	11	11%
30–39	8	8%
40–50	1	1%
60 and above	0	0%
Total	100	100%

Data from Table 2 indicates that the age group 18–28 accounts for the highest percentage of the surveyed sample, at 66%. The age group 19–29 constitutes 11%, while 30–39 represents 8%. The 40–50 age group constitutes only 1%, and those aged 60 and above represent 0%. This suggests a significant concentration of younger individuals in the sample.

Table 3: Residential Area Distribution

Residential Area	Frequency	Percentage
Urban	78	78%
Rural	22	22%
Total	100	100%

Table 3 reveals that the majority of the surveyed individuals reside in urban areas, accounting for 78%, while only 22% are from rural areas. This highlights that most of the respondents are city dwellers.

Translation to Academic English:

Table 4: Educational Level Distribution

Educational Level	Frequency	Percentage
Elementary	0	0%
High School	25	25%
Bachelor's	53	53%
Diploma	14	14%
Master's	4	4%
Doctorate	4	4%
Total	100	100%

The data in Table 4 highlights the distribution of respondents' use of social media based on their educational qualifications. Bachelor's degree holders rank first at 53%, followed by high school graduates at 25%, diploma holders at 14%, and those with a master's and doctorate degree both at 4%. These results indicate a high level of social media engagement, particularly among university-educated individuals.

Table 5: Social Media Usage

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	100	100%
No	0	0%
Total	100	100%

Table 5 shows that 100% of the respondents use social media, indicating that all individuals in the sample actively engage with social media platforms.

Table 6: General Frequency of Social Media Usage

Frequency	Frequency	Percentage
Always	89	89%
Sometimes	11	11%
Rarely	0	0%
Total	100	100%

According to Table 6, 89% of respondents indicated that they always use social media, while 11% use it sometimes, and 0% rarely use it. These findings demonstrate continuous and frequent use of social media among respondents.

Table 7: Preferred Duration of Social Media Usage

Duration	Frequency	Percentage
Less than an hour	8	8%
1–2 hours	30	30%
3–5 hours	41	41%
6 hours or more	21	21%
Total	100	100%

Table 7 illustrates the amount of time respondents spend browsing social media content. The majority (41%) reported spending 3–5 hours on social media, followed by 30% who spend 1–2 hours, 21% who spend 6 hours or more, and 8% who spend less than an hour. This indicates that most respondents use social media for three or more hours daily.

Table 8: Social Media Usage Pattern

Usage Pattern	Frequency	Percentage
Regularly	39	39%
Irregularly	55	55%
I don't know	6	6%
Total	100	100%

Table 8 reveals the respondents' patterns of social media usage. Irregular use ranks highest at 55%, followed by regular use at 39%, and 6% of respondents reported that they are unsure about their usage pattern.

Translation to Academic English:

Table 9: Times of Increased Social Media Usage

Time of Use	Frequency	Percentage
Morning	7	7%
Afternoon	9	9%
Evening	64	64%
After Midnight	20	20%
Total	100	100%

The data in Table 9 highlights the times of day when social media usage is most frequent. Evening ranks first at 64%, followed by after midnight at 20%, afternoon at 9%, and morning at 7%. This indicates that the majority of respondents prefer using social media during the evening hours.

Table 10: Most Used Social Media Platforms

Platform	Frequency	Percentage
Facebook	46	46%
YouTube	3	3%
Instagram	27	27%
Telegram	9	9%
WhatsApp	15	15%
Total	100	100%

The data in Table 10 identifies the most used social media platforms among respondents. Facebook ranks first at 46%, followed by Instagram at 27%, WhatsApp at 15%, Telegram at 9%, and YouTube at 3%. These findings underscore Facebook's prominence as the most popular platform.

Table 11: Preferred Locations for Social Media Use

Location	Frequency	Percentage
At home	94	94%
At work	4	4%
At a café	2	2%
Total	100	100%

Table 11 shows that 94% of respondents prefer using social media at home, followed by 4% at work and 2% at cafés. This highlights the home as the most common location for social media usage.

Table 12: Preferred Days for Social Media Usage

Preference	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	47	47%
No	53	53%
Total	100	100%

Table 12 illustrates whether respondents have preferred days for social media usage. The majority (53%) indicated "No," while 47% indicated "Yes," suggesting that most respondents do not have specific preferred days for social media use.

Table 13: Reasons for Preferring Certain Days for Social Media Usage

Reason	Frequency	Percentage
Holidays	82	82%
Family Gatherings	18	18%
Travel Days	0	0%
Total	100	100%

The data in Table 13 shows the reasons for preferring certain days for social media usage. Holidays rank first at 82%, followed by family gatherings at 18%. Travel days were not reported as a reason (0%). This suggests that holidays are the primary time for increased social media activity.

Table 14: Preference for Social Media to Increase Political Awareness

Preference	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	49	49%
No	13	13%
Sometimes	38	38%
Total	100	100%

Table 14 demonstrates respondents' preferences for using social media to increase political awareness. "Yes" ranks first at 49%, followed by "Sometimes" at 38%, and "No" at 13%. These results indicate that a significant portion of respondents see social media as a useful tool for political awareness.

Translation to Academic English:

Table 15: Preferred Language or Dialect for Engaging with Political News on Social Media

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Colloquial Language	45	45%
Standard Language	48	48%
Mixed (Intermediate)	7	7%
Total	100	100%

Table 15 shows the preferred language or dialect for engaging with political news on social media. Standard language ranks first at 48%, followed by colloquial language at 45%, and mixed language at 7%. This indicates that most respondents prefer standard language for discussing political topics on social media.

Table 16: Discussion Partners for Political Information from Iraqi Satellite Channels

Category	Frequency	Percentage
With friends	25	25%
With family	11	11%
With specialists	64	64%
Total	100	100%

Table 16 highlights the individuals with whom respondents discuss political information from Iraqi satellite channels. Specialists rank first at 64%, followed by friends at 25%, and family at 11%. This indicates that most respondents prefer discussing political topics with specialists.

Table 17: Iraqi Satellite Channels Contributing to Political Awareness

Channel	Frequency	Percentage
Al-Iraqiya	46	46%
Al-Sharqiya	31	31%
Al-Etejah	0	0%
Al-Sumaria	10	10%
A-News	6	6%
Zagros	7	7%
Total	100	100%

Table 17 shows which Iraqi satellite channels respondents perceive as contributing to their political awareness. Al-Iraqiya ranks first at 46%, followed by Al-Sharqiya at 31%, Al-Sumaria at 10%, Zagros at 7%, and A-News at 6%. Al-Etejah received no mentions (0%).

Table 18: Preferred Topics from Iraqi Satellite Channels on Social Media

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Political	52	52%
Social	21	21%
Service-related	11	11%
Religious	10	10%
Security-related	6	6%
Total	100	100%

Table 18 highlights the types of information respondents prefer to receive from Iraqi satellite channels on social media. Political topics rank first at 52%, followed by social topics at 21%, service-related

topics at 11%, religious topics at 10%, and security-related topics at 6%. This indicates a strong interest in political content among respondents.

Table 19: Preferred Features of Political Content on Satellite Channel Pages

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Political topics related to the government (domestic affairs)	28	28%
Content of political topics	27	27%
Politically themed content with excellent design	25	25%
Topics related to foreign political affairs	20	20%
Total	100	100%

Table 19 shows respondents' preferences for specific features of political content on satellite channel pages. Topics related to the government (domestic affairs) rank first at 28%, followed by the general content of political topics at 27%, excellently designed political topics at 25%, and foreign political topics at 20%.

Table 20: Contribution of Satellite Channel Pages on Social Media to Political Awareness

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Yes, they contribute	64	64%
No, they do not	7	7%
Sometimes	28	28%
Total	100	100%

Table 20 shows whether respondents believe satellite channel pages on social media contribute to their political awareness. "Yes, they contribute" ranks first at 64%, followed by "Sometimes" at 28%, and "No, they do not" at 7%. This indicates that most respondents find these pages helpful in enhancing their political awareness.

Translation to Academic English:

Table 21: Types of Political Information Preferred on Iraqi Satellite Channel Pages

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Political Conflicts	50	50%
Political Alliances	8	8%
Political Meetings	22	22%
International Agreements	20	20%
Total	100	100%

Table 21 outlines the types of political information respondents prefer to follow on Iraqi satellite channel pages. Political conflicts rank first at 50%, followed by political meetings at 22%, international agreements at 20%, and political alliances at 8%.

Table 22: Reasons for Following Iraqi Satellite Channel Social Media Pages

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Neutrality	26	26%
Partisanship	9	9%
To know political events	65	65%
Total	100	100%

Table 22 shows why respondents follow Iraqi satellite channel social media pages. The majority (65%) indicated that their primary reason is to know political events, followed by neutrality at 26%, and partisanship at 9%.

Table 23: Respondents' Opinions on the Nature of Political News on Satellite Channel Pages

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Objective	28	28%
Partisan	26	26%
Political	27	27%
I don't know	19	19%
Total	100	100%

Table 23 illustrates respondents' perceptions of the nature of political news presented on satellite channel pages. Objective news ranks first at 28%, followed closely by political content at 27%, partisan news at 26%, and "I don't know" at 19%.

Table 24: Level of Interaction with Satellite Channel Pages Sharing Political News

Category	Frequency	Percentage
High	29	29%
Moderate	48	48%
Low	23	23%
Total	100	100%

Table 24 indicates the level of interaction respondents have with satellite channel pages that share political news. Moderate interaction ranks highest at 48%, followed by high interaction at 29%, and low interaction at 23%.

Hypothesis Testing

First: T-Test for a Single Sample

To validate some of the study's hypotheses based on questions related to the measurement scale, a T-test for a single sample is used. This test compares the arithmetic mean to the hypothetical mean. If the arithmetic mean is greater than the hypothetical mean, this indicates statistical significance in favor of the arithmetic mean, meaning the hypothesis is positively supported. Conversely, if the arithmetic mean is smaller than the hypothetical mean, the significance is in favor of the hypothetical mean, indicating a negative or inverse application of the hypothesis.

The hypothetical mean is calculated as follows:

$$\text{Hypothetical Mean} = \frac{\text{Sum of Scale Options}}{\text{Number of Options}}$$

Hypothesis to Test:

1. Does the use of television channel pages on social media platforms contribute to increasing political awareness?

Translation to Academic English:

The results are as shown in **Table 1**:

Table 1: T-Test Results for a Single Sample

Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	Hypothetical Mean	Calculated T-Value	Degrees of Freedom	Tabular T-Value (5%)	Significance
2.58	0.09	2	62.45	99	1.97	Positive

(Table prepared by the researcher using SPSS software results.)

The calculated T-value (62.45) exceeds the tabular value at a significance level of (0.05) with 99 degrees of freedom (1.97). This indicates a significant relationship. Since the arithmetic mean of this

axis (2.58) is greater than the hypothetical mean (2), the significance favors the arithmetic mean, confirming the hypothesis in a positive direction. This demonstrates that television channel pages on social media contribute to increasing political awareness.

Second Hypothesis Testing:

The use of television channel pages on social media platforms to follow political content contributes to enhancing individuals' level of political awareness.

The results are as shown in **Table 2**:

Table 2: T-Test Results for a Single Sample

Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	Hypothetical Mean	Calculated T-Value	Degrees of Freedom	Tabular T-Value (5%)	Significance
2.36	0.10	2	38.74	99	1.97	Positive

(Table prepared by the researcher using SPSS software results.)

The calculated T-value (38.74) exceeds the tabular value at a significance level of (0.05) with 99 degrees of freedom (1.97). This indicates a significant relationship. Since the arithmetic mean of this axis (2.36) is greater than the hypothetical mean (2), the significance favors the arithmetic mean, confirming the hypothesis in a positive direction. This demonstrates that the use of television channel pages on social media to follow political content contributes to increasing political awareness.

Recommendations:

1. **Enhance Interaction:** Strengthen engagement between television channels on social media platforms and their audience by providing interactive and direct content.
2. **Focus on Objectivity:** Prioritize presenting objective and unbiased political news content to enhance the credibility of satellite channel pages.
3. **Adopt Modern Methods:** Media institutions should diversify their presentation of political events by using modern methods such as infographics, graphic designs, and short content formats.

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